

Wireless SCADA for Remote Industrial Monitoring using NI-MyRio Labview and Grafana

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Abstract

SCADA controls are limited by how much scholarship can be done with them, due to the high price and proprietary nature of these industrial monitoring systems. In this paper, we present an inexpensive wireless SCADA architecture for remotely obtaining levels within a PLC managed level station to be integrated with an NI myRIO from national instruments. The data from the process will be stored in real time using LabVIEW; this data will also be used to create a living excel dataset that can easily be moved between lab environments and into other systems for analysis and export. The final platform for this developed system is an Intel UP Squared embedded computer that runs Windows 10. Using this device we will run Grafana to create a dashboard that allows access to all historical data, as well as access to live trend information. Additionally, by using wireless communication we reduce installation complexity and provide the ability to access systems remotely in mobile devices as well using IOT. The proposed method eliminates the need for traditional SCADA control programs which allow for increased